

Media(ted) Data Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

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CONTENTS

CONTENTS	1
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS	2
THE MEDIA(TED) DATA INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITY	4
OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS	4
WORKSHOP 1	5
WORKSHOP 2	8
NEXT STEPS	13
APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP 1 RESPONSES	14
APPENDIX 2: WORKSHOP 2 RESPONSES	28

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. In early 2024 we initiated a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure.

One of the proposed new activity areas is *Media(ted) Data*. This ARDC investment aims to support new methodologies to access and analyse diverse types of digital trace data and observe online interactions. We see an opportunity to support cutting-edge research on social, economic, health, and environmental issues and to analyse and understand the benefits and risks associated with digital platforms.

The ARDC is co-designing its new infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders to ensure that we create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

The ARDC conducted two co-design workshops in February 2024 to shape plans for this investment opportunity. These workshops were open to all, and were attended by a total of 73 participants from 29 organisations, including Australian universities, GLAM organisations and research infrastructure providers. In Workshop 1 we refined our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and found out what outcomes participants hoped to see. In Workshop 2 we explored how the desired outcomes could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and discussed requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities.

The 2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap identified avenues to enhance the impact of HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research, proposing improvements in coordinating research infrastructure to facilitate access to and analysis of physical and digital collections. These improvements involve leveraging tools like digitization, aggregation, and interpretation platforms.

Subsequently, the Australian Government Department of Education commissioned three studies to pinpoint investment-ready programs eligible for National Research Infrastructure funding. While not all recommendations from these studies received funding initially, the identified activities demonstrated a high level of readiness to engage with and benefit from the development of a [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

From 2022-2024 the ARDC-led HASS and Indigenous RDC has implemented a number of these activities, including:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities (IIRC) led by Dist Prof Marcia Langton, University of Melbourne
- Establishing the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA) led by Prof Michael Haugh, University of Queensland
- Developing Integrated Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences (IRISS) led by A/Prof Steven McEachern, Australian National University
- Creating the Trove Researcher Platform, which comprised Trove Enhancements (led by ANU) and the ARDC Community Data Lab (led by the ARDC)

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

Our commitment extends to supporting existing activities such as IIRC, LDA, the Community Data Lab, and Social Sciences while also considering the expansion of the RDC to include new activities for Creative Arts and Media(ted) Data. It has become evident that sustained investment is crucial to scale up these activities and provide coordinated digital research infrastructure meeting the needs of humanities, arts, social sciences, and Indigenous researchers.

Phase 2 aims to consolidate previous efforts, capitalise on synergies between existing and new projects, broaden partnerships and disciplinary coverage, and deepen engagement with the GLAM sector and Indigenous data governance.

In developing new activities, we have considered researcher needs gathered from consultations in 2021 and identified areas with active, coherent communities where research infrastructure can flourish. We have also looked at existing infrastructure that could be bolstered to transition into enduring national assets.

THE MEDIA(TED) DATA INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITY

In the era of digitisation, Australia's digital platforms have become integral to daily life, influencing commerce, social interactions, and community formation. The resulting data is a rich source of information about these aspects of Australian society. However, the fragmented nature of this data across various platforms presents challenges in data availability and standardisation. Ethical and legal considerations around the personal and/or sensitive nature of this data are compounded by this fragmentation.

The current limitations in our ability to comprehend and harness the vast data generated by digital platforms call for innovative tools and approaches. This ARDC investment aims to support new methodologies to access and analyse diverse types of digital trace data and observe online interactions. We see an opportunity to support cutting-edge research on social, economic, health, and environmental issues and to analyse and understand the benefits and risks associated with digital platforms.

A plan to address this challenge is being developed through a process of co-design in collaboration with RMIT University, Queensland University of Technology, the University of Queensland, the University of Melbourne, Swinburne University and Deakin University. Collaborating initiatives include the ARC Centre of Excellence for Automated Decision-Making + Society (ADM+S), the ARC Centre of Excellence for the Digital Child, and the Australian Digital Observatory.

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

Problem Identification has taken place through extensive consultations and information gathering sessions, as described above. By tracking emerging gaps, opportunities, and sectoral trends, the ARDC has identified potential avenues for delivering benefits to the HASS and Indigenous research community. This strategic delineation of opportunities reflects the ARDC's commitment to addressing pertinent challenges and fostering innovation within the HASS and Indigenous research landscape.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the two open co-design workshops described below. Workshops were advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure

provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

WORKSHOP 1

The first co-design workshop was held virtually on 1 February 2024. It was attended by 42 participants from 19 organisations. Organisations represented included 13 Australian universities, as well as medical research, industry, GLAM, and research infrastructure organisations.

The aim of this first workshop was to refine our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and find out what outcomes participants want to achieve.

Professor Julian Thomas (RMIT) and Professor Dan Angus (QUT) presented on the challenge, which they summarised with the following problem statement:

“Vast quantities of information are generated by our interactions with digital platforms, which now play a critical role in almost every aspect of Australia’s economy and society, yet our capacities to analyse large-scale social data are still very limited. Australian researchers need access to new tools and facilities to collect and analyse diverse types of social data - text, image, audio, video etc - from a wide range of online platforms. Such a capability would enable researchers across HASS and STEM, as well as government, industry and civil society, to benefit from the insights derived from social data. Opening up the ‘black box’ of digital platforms and their algorithms is essential for an expanding digital economy and society, for effective regulation and legislation to protect and enhance the digital experience for consumers, businesses and the community, and to ensure we have responsible, ethical and inclusive online spaces for all.”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

- What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?
 - Access to data is difficult (and platforms actively work to deny access)
 - There are many platforms - need for shared tools to address them (although noted that tools do exist)
 - Ethical and legal issues around data access and use
 - Data is often supplied in hard-to-use structures
 - Social data is large and diverse (but scale may not be the most pressing problem)
 - Defining the problem - it's important to be clear about what kinds of data/platforms are in scope
- Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)
 - Researchers
 - Digital platform users
 - Broader society
 - Civil organisations that observe or use digital platforms
 - Government and policy makers
 - Industry
- What limitations are created by this challenge?
 - Legal and ethical barriers to sharing data
 - Difficulty of capturing the context required to understand data
 - Effort required to access and use data - especially for non-experts
- What could we achieve by addressing it?
 - Increase skills and share methods amongst researchers
 - Increase data access
 - Understand and counteract misinformation
 - Understand the influence of digital platforms
 - Understand public perceptions of important issues

- Inform policy
- Who could benefit?
 - Researchers
 - Industry
 - Government and policy makers
 - Society more broadly

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

- What outcomes would be beneficial?
 - Improved access to and sharing of data
 - Greater visibility of available data
 - Increased technical skills
 - Shared tools for working with data
 - Guidance on methods - what is best practice? What is possible with particular kinds of data?
 - Guidance on the ethical and legal aspects of working with this kind of data
 - Communities of practice
 - Enable interdisciplinary collaboration
 - Improve visibility across the research landscape
 - Agreed standards for data and metadata
 - Better research
 - Changes to policy governing digital platforms
- What existing infrastructure/activities could we build on?
 - Participants gave an extensive list of existing platforms, organisations and initiatives that could be leveraged - see Appendix 1

Activity 3: Roles and partners

- What other kinds of partners need to be involved?

- The digital platforms themselves (although noted this could be a risk given the sometimes adversarial relationships between platforms and those seeking to access their data)
- Indigenous communities
- Civil society organisations monitoring platforms
- Government and policy makers
- Users of the infrastructure
- Research institutions
- Industry
- Disciplinary organisations
- What other expertise/resources would benefit the project?
 - Technical skills (with a note about the importance of retaining technical staff)
 - Expertise in training
 - Expertise in ethics, consent and the law
- Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?
 - Indigenous communities
 - Linguistically diverse populations
 - Users of digital platforms

WORKSHOP 2

The second co-design workshop was held virtually on 12 February 2024. It was attended by 53 participants from 23 organisations. Organisations represented included 16 Australian universities, an international university, as well as GLAM and research infrastructure organisations.

The aim of this workshop was to explore how the desired outcomes identified by participants in Workshop 1 could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and understand requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

Staff from the ARDC reported back on the key findings from Workshop 1. Based on the responses to the Workshop 1 question “What outcomes would be beneficial”, we drew out four high-level outcome themes:

1. “Making it easier for researchers to source, share and access mediated data”, based on responses about improving data sharing and access, and the visibility of data.
2. “Sharing analytical methods and increasing technical ability in researchers working with mediated data”, based on responses about the need for guidance on methods, shared tools, and increasing technical skills.
3. “Increasing coherence and collaboration across groups and disciplines working with mediated data”, based on responses about communities of practice, interdisciplinary collaboration, the need for agreed standards, and enabling better visibility of the research landscape.
4. “Develop protocols and guidance for governance and ethics.”

Responses from Workshop 1 also covered outcomes around improving research and supporting changes in policy - rather than addressing these directly, we see them as being enabled by the four outcomes above.

We addressed each of these four outcome themes in turn. For each theme, Professor Julian Thomas (RMIT) and Professor Dan Angus (QUT) outlined a range of approaches and solutions that could be taken to achieve that outcome. In breakout groups, the workshop participants discussed those approaches, noting any requirements they would have for these approaches to be successful, and any practical considerations to be taken into account. Participants recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Common themes from the responses are recorded below, and full responses are attached in Appendix 2.

Making it easier for researchers to source, share and access mediated data

- Approach: Making use of existing platform APIs
 - “APIs are a small part of the ecosystem now”
 - “There are thousands of APIs and sources of data - who decides what should be included?”
 - Need for improved documentation for APIs, and ability to share researcher-generated documentation
- Approach: Developing apps and mobile plugins
 - Support for mobile tools - “most interaction with digital platforms is via mobile apps and interfaces so we need to study them at this interface”.
 - Full-screen capture is desirable but also has privacy concerns
- Approach: Developing browser extensions

- Approach: Developing crowdsourcing platforms
 - Questions about the sustainability and ethics of crowdsourcing
 - Ensuring diversity as well as scale
- Approach: Enabling participants to donate data requested from platforms (“data donation packages”)
 - Importance of data and metadata standards
 - Quality assurance
 - Ensuring participants have the right to donate data/copyright concerns
- Approach: Creating synthetic data via generative AI
 - Ensuring transparency and understandability of algorithms
- Approach: Web scraping
 - Scraping vs archiving
 - Particular legal and ethical concerns
 - Training required for best practice
- Other themes from responses
 - Importance of good models for consent
 - Data sourcing approaches are most effective in combination

Sharing analytical methods and increasing technical ability in researchers working with mediated data

- Approach: Machine learning tools
 - Increasing the ease and accessibility of tool use with LLM assistance
 - Use of Gen-AI for a first-pass understanding of data
 - Use of Gen-AI and other tools to support analysis with minimal coding
- Approach: Developing crowdsourcing platforms
 - Maintain a standing panel of trusted participants
 - Ensuring representativeness of participants
 - Important to have meaningful tasks for participants with clear outcomes
- Approach: Tools for text and image analytics

- Machine learning clustering of text and images
- Support for multimodal analysis
- Standardised tools and approaches
- Reproducible workflows in browser-based tools
- Approach: Test environments for simulation experiments
 - Need for continuous updating - shared environments split this burden
 - Test environments that can be used by non-technical people
- Approach: ADO ecosystem
 - Value of ADO's high-quality, modular tools
- Visualisation
 - Visualisation to explore data as well as present results
 - Use of Gen-AI for building and refining visualisations
- Other themes
 - Considerations of sustainability and ongoing maintenance
 - Need for a code repository solution

Increasing coherence and collaboration across groups and disciplines working with mediated data

- Labelling and annotations
 - Annotations from community members/people with lived experience
 - Techniques to “unflatten” data recorded as screen capture images
- Harmonisation
 - Ability to harmonise data depends on data types and usages
 - Use of international standards for identifiers
- Classification
 - Development of community-driven classification schemas
- Linked data
 - Ethical and privacy concerns related to increasing identifiability of data

- LDaCA and CDL are using RO-Crate (schema.org based data description for both data assets and rich context)
- Linked data implies infrastructure for storing and identifying data
- Integration
 - Standard formats and interfaces
 - Modular tools that work together

Develop protocols and guidance for governance and ethics

- Ethics
 - Different risk considerations for research datasets and data archives
 - Providing guidance on these kinds of data and research for ethics committees
- Legal
 - Need for national platforms for storing sensitive data
 - Requires a high level of legal advice
- Data management
 - Storage - where can data be stored once research projects are over?
 - Need for storage and protocols for sensitive data - institutions may not have these existing
- Training
 - Leverage existing programs and connect to existing providers (UK Open Data Institute, the Carpentries)
 - Mentorships to build skills (but note difficulty in scaling these)
 - Share training materials and templates for training between institutions
 - Data sprints and hackathons
- Outreach
 - Outreach and awareness raising are necessary for uptake
- Collaboration
 - Actively reach out to groups with overlapping interests - particularly internationally
- Participation

- Incentives and recognition for participation in research
- Ensuring representative participation
- Other themes
 - Differentiating legal and ethical issues

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close at the end of day, Friday 22 March. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2024.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line “Media(ted) Data”.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP 1 RESPONSES

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inaccessibility of large platforms == need to access small platforms, implications: shift to multi-platform analytics, need for ever more collection tools etc ● Platforms, technology vendors, and other entities are making it increasingly difficult to gather user experience data. Either through obtuse standards, obfuscation of code, or other walled-gardens. We need better approaches to gather data that we not already have access to, or are actively prevented to access for various, largely commercial, reasons. ● tech companies' control over access and structure of data. ● Where do researchers stand when they can technically collect data outside a platform's ToS? Will your institution support Fair Use etc.... ● The primary problem is to get access to data in commercial platforms rather than analysing data which is available ● denied access to social platforms ● Access to platforms is difficult/denied by commercial owners (+1) ● "Access to platforms is difficult..." - yes, the proposed infrastructure is often fundamentally about creating workarounds to this access problem ● Those with capabilities often don't have access and often have to use "toy data sets". Those with access to the data , don't know what to do with it. ● Issue of data availability is not a new problem! It's a groundhog day issue! (+1) ● Trying to access the data we don't have. ● Some social media data is by its nature un archivable and inaccessible ● Commercial entities not wanting to play or release key data, making set very incomplete and patchy ● Problem and benefit for areas and issues of 'data scarcity' - lowering the cost of access to human and social data

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● There are already heaps of tools, methods, approaches to analysing various kinds of data - do not agree that existing tools are as limited as stated (+1) ● It'd be good for the problem statement to name the need to not just study social data but to use that social data in order to observe, investigate the automated models of digital platforms - I think this is implied in the 'black box' claim but could be made clearer. Studying the 'models' is what makes this program different to existing tools and methods ● We need shared measurement tools for research (e.g., how do we capture what is misinformation? What is online hate?) ● Privacy and security issues play critical party ● Problem statement needs to address ethical, political, privacy and legal implications associated with this type of research. It is not politically neutral. ● Limited by platform terms of service ● How do we define the parts of this problem? What is bias? ● Maybe the problem is as much about defining and scope and that dilemma needs to go into the problem statement ● change social data to mediated data ● support the problem statement - but what is social data? ● term 'social data' may not encompass the full range of platform/platform-mediated data we need to explore ● how about defining the term in mission statement to refer to platform-derived/platform-mediated data whose analysis is in the public interest - or something like that ● i think it would be really valuable if the definition could include things like recs, ads, promos, user navigation data, search query data etc - not just traditional social media data ((posts, comments, etc) ● the lack of technical and financial capacities in HASS in developing and using effective tools for data scraping. ● The statement could perhaps refer to challenges involved with reproducibility and research quality. ● There is a sense of urgency now with AI etc ● RE: Data supply, the applied research & practice shows that devolution (vs. centralization) of data (collection, use & sharing) is considered best

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>practice. Champions of national open gov projects are systematically being defunded (starting with USA in 2017). (+1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Should we capture the challenge of new types of synthetic social data, e.g. from generative AI? ● A big problem we are & will be facing is LOST DATA due to defunding of programs, APIs that are discontinued/no longer supported. ● I think we need to be careful not to over-problematise the digital world in framing the challenges (+1) ● Scatter, diversity - Australian, international, how do we bring it together? ● social data is big, messy, fuzzy ● social data need not be big, need not be messy, need not be fuzzy ● Problem statement doesn't match the presentation - this is entirely defined by "large scale", but the presentation speaks to more situated, context specific (even experiential uses) ● Over-focuses on large "scale" - I don't think the scale of data is a problem here so much as about matching (or collecting) appropriate data to fit research questions

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researchers, civil society groups interested in observation of digital platforms, and also users who want to donate and explore their own experience of automated cultures. Everyday users of digital platforms are critical because they are both critical to how the infrastructure will work (through donation, etc.) and important end-users of the tools. (+1) ● civil society organisation working on advocacy issues eg public health campaigns (+1) ● Q: Can we expand this to beyond the research community to include civil society and beyond? ● all sectors of research academia and wider society ● Impact of the challenge is very broad across civil society, those who will actively participate will be mediated data researchers -- maybe a quest is to expand this group via the ARDC investment? ● everyone, but do we need different solutions for diff industries. ● The challenges affect all. Even if one is not directly involved/participating others are, which has whole of society implications ● End Users of the digitalised public services; Service providers, researchers ● Also affects citizens in their ability to understand their own 'digital and data footprint' (+2) ● challenge of platformisation affects everyone; the research infrastructure is of most interest to researchers, policymakers, students, also some sectors of industry ● researchers, policy makers, political advisors ● Govt - do not realise the data even exists ● researchers working in advancing knowledge on better algorithms (e.g., search engines or recommender systems) to build more realistic test collections ● People who turn away from online research because of ideas that it's "too hard" (+1) ● The problem statement needs to be more clear who the target audience is (i.e., researchers (narrow) or civil society to include civil government (wide)) (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "The problem statement needs to be more clear ... researchers... or civil society?" Can't it be all of those? ● Privacy and security issues affect anyone who wants to access the (sensitive) data, there will be a long process to "clear" ethics, security, etc. ● Express research humility -- Leverage what others have done. You are unlikely to be the first one facing any given problem. Join a working group, community group within a research data community and be part of the solution! ● AKA "don't recreate the wheel" :-)
<p>What limitations are created by this challenge?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● finding relevance in the data point is a big challenge ● Capturing entire social context of any single social data point is difficult, decreasing usefulness (e.g. capturing that Jane said "Yuk" really needs to data about what else was happening in conversation) ● User experiences on platforms may vastly differ. There are 2 limitations: Context and representation in the dataset. (+1) ● Legal and ethical issues with sharing collected data (+2) ● ethics committees, legal offices in our unis might be a barrier to using this and we might not be able to - for example - share our data ● safety of researchers and users of data, reliability of data, ability to quantify ● Access to government data is limited and hierarchical ● Even limited studies would be very important if they are soundly based, comprehensive within their boundaries, etc. God to be realistic about expectations. ● Some data / tools needs to be created in "simulated sandboxes" to test the implications of new tools for generating synthetic data ● A challenge is the relationships with platforms and their role in shaping and thwarting approaches to observability ● Research on mediated data is not comparable and cumulative, and it is and politically contested (+1) ● This infrastructure will be designed around current research paradigms of the digital, social etc. How to ensure it's built to last? ● Overwhelm and apathy (+1) ● it's hard for non-experts to use social data in research

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What could we achieve by addressing it?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support the training and skilling of RSE's who can Build tooling to assist (there is a lack of skilled and available tech folk in Aus) ● Raising (social media) data methods in different disciplines could lead to more work and consensus in comparative methods, so we can advance the field by being better able to compare studies and results ● discrepancy in digital literacy and methods.. if we build this, we can start build on studies for comparable methods to increase the digital literacy ● Many researchers lack basic data skills (other than filing PDFs, docx files). Researcher tech literacy is needed, but it has to be rewarded by the institutions they work for. If researchers are not "judged" (measured) by their data practices, it won't happen. ● Democracy? Tracking more about mis/dis information in social data shows where undue influence is happening? (+3) ● "Tracking... undue influence" and natural, e.g. not undue, influence in society ● push against misinformation - supports those who promote accountability ● There is a potential for society to enhance its comprehension of the nuanced perceptions and lived experiences related to current geopolitical issues and their intersection with policy and government. ● The last sentence misses out on describing the benefits of the research which could take place with this research infrastructure and the impact that might have on policy.ie. The research benefits have disappeared. ● The potential for research data capture would be hugely positive ● streamlining the authorisation process to access the data ● enable multiple stakeholders get the pulse or public perceptions on important societal issues ● Reimagine futures that we can't currently see ● A charter to begin with addressing ethics and rights of people. ● Accountability ● Digital literacies taught in schools but via platforms themselves

QUESTION	RESPONSES
Who could be benefited by addressing this challenge?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Benefits everyone throughout - can we map the flow of impact? ● Could we create a charter that frames the desired beneficiaries and ethical principles? ● Startups seeking data, with a priority on enabling socially-oriented and indigenous startups. ● the platforms themselves ● Those benefiting might include the platforms themselves. This would suggest partnerships with these platforms. ● It could benefit the public ● Liberal democracies worldwide ● Children and families able to learn and evaluate what is happening on platforms and how the algorithms work (+1) ● Government agencies, policy makers ● Students and early career researchers without access to data infrastructures (+1) ● there's a huge benefit here in empowering AU researchers to implement best-practice in platform research - avoid duplication of efforts, time wasted, ineffective research investment, etc

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

QUESTION	RESPONSES
What outcomes would be beneficial?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● guidance available for new researchers using social data - guidance in respect of ethical use of data/ 'how to' tools ● Governance and ethical guidelines for data archiving/sharing ● Making it simpler to navigate legal/ethical requirements in doing research using social data (+1) ● Develop strong governance and ethics protocols for data donation, sharing data, building and training models, etc. (+1) ● Reform of privacy/ unnecessary retaining and use of user personal data ... make it clearer to users what is there about them, so prompt more public appetite to limit unethical data use by commercial platforms (+1) ● Infrastructure as always is not the be all and end all -- equally important is policy, community, partn ● Better policies that enable us to share data with the researchers

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● develop policies around safety for users of digital platforms as well as researchers ● Policy advancement around making sure platforms are making their data available for transparency and accountability purposes (as in EU) ● Better research question ● More and better research and more situated and more specific study of understanding online world/digital lives/platforms ● community of practice - across sectors as well as interdisciplinarity between researchers ● Better interdisciplinary collaboration .. working with social data was too hard for those not expert researchers, now engineers or medical researchers can use a system easily & gain insights into social data about their research question ● better cross disciplinary ● standards for data ● Metadata, metadata, metadata! Demographics, locations, dates etc. ● Strong communities of practice in social data and analysis (+3) ● state-of-the-art for researching particular platforms ● researcher-friendly explainers on the data possibilities of particular platforms (e.g., "i need to understand all the data available from/ways i can study Uber/Amazon/whatever" - can the infrastructure help me?) ● field guides - best-practice methods surveys ● Enable researchers to enhance collaboration by sharing data and validated measurement tools (e.g. classifiers) ● simple tools for knowing what areas people are focusing on ● Tooling/platform re-use e.g. "build once use many times" ● What tools GLAM sector might need to collect digital born material? the tools/PL we develop out of this can be beneficial. ● Replacing dysfunctional platform tools. ● Connect toolmakers with researchers as a collaboration ● Sandbox for users to try out Gen AI tech to explore the possibilities ● More accessible tools ● I would like to see a way of working with data that has been recorded and digitised where the language is not a written one. This is a common issue with Indigenous data - being recorded with spelling that makes the literary record unlinked and difficult to find in digital search.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Linking digital social data to other vocabularies and data ● Developing partnerships with industry for specific projects ● Sustainable platforms! ● Technical and social capacity to observe automated models of digital platforms. The social bit is important - a shift so that researchers, civil society and government no longer thing of these as impenetrable 'black boxes' - but rather as something that can be observed and accountable ● improved collaboration w/ civil society orgs ● Opportunity to understand engagement with research beyond academia ● Cross platform studies (+1) ● Deep fakes are very embedded in social/digital platforms now. if we can achieve the outcomes, we can achieve better reporting of this to the govt. ● A sense that we are 'running with' platforms, rather than constantly trying to catch up ● central area of resources ● Providing a simple view of own social data footprint by users, by accessing all info in one central point? (Like havebeenpwned but whathaveisaidwhere) ● Infrastructures (plural) ● curating scholarship on this field of research ● mapping what other researchers across Aus are working on ● Being able to explore the data before even downloading it ● visibility of what data is available, where, and how it can be accessed ● Develop a comprehensive colour coded data visualisation that overviews the various international public and private data sets known/available e.g., forming a knowledge repository of the range of data sources, data or skill set (for research methods) available. Perhaps a flow chart for how the research infrastructure 'hangs together'. ● Growing the pool of technical skilled pool to do this work (+2) ● Incredible potential for people to learn remotely, on country - skill uplift ● increasing skills of researchers ● Retention of skilled technical researchers pas Post-Doc work (+3) ● Simple interface or a PL to go fetch data or twitter data via simple VM or something

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop new approaches to social media data and data collection in the post API era ● Enable research to collect new social (or mediated) data supporting existing and new research project ● Allow researchers to access users' legacy data ● Having agreed protocols for how to get data that researchers/institutions can follow ● Greater awareness for access of data and tools in this space ● Even at the cost of recency, scale etc it would be good to have some iconic, well-provnced data sets which could be studied by multiple researchers. ● a few outcomes here: (1) hands-on access to different data sets; (2) leveraging methodological expertise and innovation- it's not just about the data that the infrastructure will host, but also what the infrastructure can do for researchers grappling with methodological questions, frustrations, etc
<p>What existing infrastructure/ activities could we build on?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GLAM organisations in general ● web archives (+1) ● web archiving toolkits ● Vocabularies and standards ● Australasia's research software engineering (RSE) community ● collaboration ● Probes and experimental innovations -- what are the ripple effects? ● Benchmark environments ● Generative AI as an accessibility strategy for datasets ● Engineering students. Toolmaking as assessment projects ● GDPR Data Dump style ● Standards and leaderboards for testing ● Python libraries and other code repositories to support researchers ● learn from data donation and crowdsourcing from other disciplines - i.e. medicine ● existing citizen science platforms ● Health data donation and crowdsourcing tools ● ABS style de-identification ● Sensitive data governance structures ● Data governance and access to sensitive data? (+1)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UK data services, open access data ● legacy data (+1) ● Data collected by individual researchers that could be shared ● Wikidata ● Data around user-online engagement with GLAM collections -- eg search queries in library catalogues; Trove annotations. ● Trove and NSLA web archives ● Commercial systems such as mechanical turk or brankwatch ● data collection efforts of media regulators - ACMA, European Audiovisual Observatory ● international developments eg NIO in the US ● Wikipedia ● Digital Methods Initiative ● some private providers e.g. Ampere Analysis ● Australian Longitudinal Study of Women's Health ● UK's Smart Data programme: https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/smart-data-research-uk/ ● benchmark environments to systematically test different solutions for a particular problem. E.g., see TIRA: https://webis.de/research/tira.html ● Australian Digital Observatory (ADO) (+1) ● Australian Text Analytics Platform/LADAL (+1) ● Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA) (+1) ● Australian Ad Observatory (+1) ● AURIN ● Virtual Observatory for the Study of Online Networks (VOSON) labs ● Community Data Lab (CDL) ● Australian search experience (ADM+S) ● Nectar (+1) ● GLAM Workbench -- web archive tools, GLAM user data ● KeyPoint ● "Keypoint" - Keypoint is a secure data platform for accessing and analysing sensitive data - SeRP is another example. ● SeRP

QUESTION	RESPONSES

Activity 3: Roles and partners

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What other kinds of partners need to be involved?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ethics and Legal advisers (+1) ● Existing research infrastructure ● International partnerships with similar projects eg NIO ● expertise in governance structures ● Educators (to create talent infrastructure) ● embed the infrastructure in disciplinary training - eg digital methods summer schools ● End users of digital platforms ● Disciplinary orgs - to translate and promote benefits to their research communities ● at the cusp of issues and design Apple , Amazon , Alphabet , Meta Platforms , Microsoft , Nvidia , and Tesla ● Commercial social media platforms - need a carrot or stick to play nicely ● Platforms as partners are a risk. (suggest explicitly not partnering with platforms) (Platforms as adversarial operators) ● Go all out to recruit platforms as partners ● the platforms themselves ● Peak community organisations and community bodies monitoring for example online hate (e.g. Islamophobia Register, Call it out, etc) (+1) ● civil society groups with strong interest and involvement in platform and/or industry observability and accountability ● First Nations community Advisors and experts (+2) ● representatives from platforms, industries, elders and community leaders ● Vocabulary experts and systems ● Research management specialises, data librarians ● Those doing the technical work need to be involved in the whole project so they dont leave for better pay. (+2) ● policy stakeholders - ensure it's usable/user-friendly for them

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● think widely about potential users of the tools in the training aspect of the project but not necessarily as partners in ● need groups of multidisciplinary researchers to test the tools and work collaboratively on them as well as industry users ● Full research institutional buy-in (eg university research offices and research leadership) ● Libraries, universities, local government, industry
<p>What other expertise/ resources would benefit the project?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Philosophers of communication (+3) ● How do we identify/ reach/ communicate with the diverse HASS and Indigenous research communicate, and wider research disciplines that the final output is available to use for research (and that it may help them answer their research question) ● Experience from other NCRIS facilities ● citizen science project expertise (+1) ● Non-English speaker users of the platforms (+1) ● Wellbeing researchers - how to create safe platforms that may contain non contextualised upsetting and disturbing material that has been harvested from elsewhere ● Artists who may have novel and interesting use of services/platforms like this ● Commercial cloud providers ● Well supported research software engineers, with permanent jobs and career pathways. (+7) ● Technical project managers, not just programmers (+1) ● Research Software analysts too... (+1) ● technical staff (+2) ● Elders in community (1) ● Community leaders, including leaders of faith and religion ● resources/training to help researchers USE available data ● Training and access to expertise to collect the right data for a project (1) ● Legal/ethical advice (+1) ● Legal experts

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Indigenous Cultural perspectives (+5) ● activist groups involved in making safe spaces online ● ML engineers and cutting edge computer scientists for new horizons of tech and next challenges ● Culturally and linguistically diverse priority populations (1) ● Include different political views in the stakeholders or consultations,, to avoid politicising this project (and risk of defunding if there are changes in decision makers) (+1) ● Input from young people using social media (+1) ● Community elders ● guidance on flow-on consent for sharing data (+2) ● practical input from communities who work with language that does not traditionally have a written form ● wonder if we need to converse with people from national ethics guidelines? National statement may need changing as a result of work? ● People working in health ● data providers (individuals) - knowing the implications of providing their data (+1) ● A representative of a board of experts. ie the charter leader

APPENDIX 2: WORKSHOP 2 RESPONSES

Outcome 1: Making it easier for researchers to source, share and access mediated data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
APIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I think data providers need more focus on shared data publication standards to facilitate interoperability ● Apis/web scraping are a way of harvesting data, but sourcing, sharing access can be done through full-stack services, e.g. https://newstalk.digitalobservatory.net.au/ ● APIs are a small part of the ecosystem now ● There are thousands of APIs and sources of data - who decides what should be included? ● ADO has extensive experience with API data collection ● APIs need to be properly documented, with example code and tools. Researchers can create and share such documentation where the API provider doesn't (eg GLAM Workbench) ● Wikipedia has an API but not always helpful for HASS researchers (and doesn't include IP address data that can be made available through agreements with the Wikimedia Foundation. What would be useful would be help docs for HASS researchers querying the API and more formal arrangements with WMF HQ, for example, in managing (anonymised) IP data. ● Use Gen-AI to access various different APIs on the fly using a coherent interface. - Let the AI figure out the differences under the hood. ● API data collection is relatively easier in terms of ethics and data governance as it aligns with Terms of Service ● costs of researcher and/or institutional access to commercial APIs - how managed via a commons infrastructure?
Apps and mobile plugins	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Combinations of the above are also important, e.g. data donation that also use existing APIs, and also scraping. ● This is where tool development for capture of data from mobile apps would have a huge impact. Most established utilities aren't mobile-first. (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● tools for using mobile phones, most interaction with digital platforms is via mobile apps and interfaces so we need to study them at this interface (+1) ● Web recorder/ web archiving toolkit on mobile device would be very useful to support HASS researchers doing small data collections ● A comparison tool similar to comparing health funds for understanding differences between apps and plug ins. (+1) ● We need an accessibility plugin for Android. This will do the full-screen data capture that everyone wants. That's the OS way to do it. ● It's possible to capture through a proxy (man-in-the-middle attack) with web archiving tools but it wont capture what's going on with the current view ● "It's possible to capture through a proxy..." - Microservices architecture ● This is going to be tricky - privacy-preserving screen capture is likely the best option (+1)
Browser extensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● there is an increasing demand for mulitmodal ways of researching using non-traditional- we use google drive now but there should be a more securer platform ● mobile browser functionality ● Many extensions have a very short live span ● Operating models that make small projects viable - maintain trust with large, diverse groups of donators ● Informed consent must be easy to implement (e.g. PISCF upon download/launch)
Crowdsourcing platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Human support, for workflow definition and community management needs investment to support this goal. ● unsure how much of a future this has tbh; but the idea of an Australian public service alt to Amazon Turk would be nice ● e.g. using qualtrics with templates? (+1) ● "e.g. using qualtrics with templates?" - or more sophisticated ones, e.g., to collect data in an interactive way, which may involve the use of customised web applications ● Can use Gen-AI to replace crowdsourcing for a lot of tasks these days - more ethical than asking people to work for free, and much more scalable.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Complementary ways to recruit participants from diverse cohorts, i.e., large-scale studies but also less limited to geographical or cultural barriers ● is crowdsourcing sustainable ● communicating research back to the public ● It would be good to have some other platforms considered. Gaming data is an example that is often missed when considering "social media" data. ● Ethical considerations of crowdsourcing work - minimum wage for workers? +1 ● Assisting researchers on designing crowdsourcing tasks, e.g., effective ways to maintain quality of tasks (attention checks...), library of reusable instruments (pre-task questionnaires, psychometrics, etc.)
Data donation packages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Surely there needs to be an overarching use case/scenario before deciding what data should be included? ● QA will be important, both algorithmic and human-mediated. ● Standard format and tools to convert/validate the data formatting. Also need to ensure correct metadata are donated as a package. ● Copy rihght issues and data standards ● Most of our Institutional holdings have not yet been digitised and are hard copy ● Donation of what and to whom and for what purpose? +1 ● Comprehensive metadata to make the data reusable ● Needs to have some qualitative details if available. different data sets may have different information available. ● Rights of content creators to donate, including any restrictions on access to or use of their data ? ● Privacy assessments are required on information that we provide before we can provide it ● Consent will need to be fulsome, presumably allowing for the possibility of specific use of data, and also aggregation into wider datasets. ● Granular recording of consent ● Tools for data donation from specific users for particular purposes - so the tools are infrastructure but the data should be context specific and ideally embedded in meaningful citizen science partnerships

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Generative AI and synthetic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How to understand algorithms behind generative AI ● "How to understand algorithms behind generative AI" - Ensuring data can be properly referenced would be important ● Reproducibility, transparency, and building expertise in research software test engineering is going to be important. We have under-invested in research test maturity since year dot. ● How to understand algorithms behind generative AI? ● "How to understand algorithms behind generative AI?" - How to determine authorship / ownership ? ● Gen-AI can be used for synthetic data but is much more useful in understanding your real data. The use case here is to do a quick first pass of RA work, understanding entire corpuses of data quickly and then presenting a summary to a researcher. Then iterating with the researcher or RA to refine the concepts and themes drawn from the corpus. ● communicating research back to the public ● I presume that exploring and if necessary mitigating potential problems of model collapse and/or data corruption are implicit in this. It's great to see but pioneering. ● Build suitable tools that can be integrated into AI pipelines and called by the LLM to achieve work that is deterministic or better done by another process. AI can be trained to be good at methods and tool use. ● Huge potential here to simulate different user personas and investigate the different media experiences they would be offered by platforms. ● AI bots can be used to simulate persona to allow for scaled data collection. They can be built upon a real persona and cloned, or altered to look at variables. Might be useful for looking into algorithmic personalisation ● love using them so simulate a persona and e.g. test survey questions , but I would hesitate to draw firm conclusions without then going and asking those questions to real humans! ● ...and different answers to same queries across time and services ● Clarification on what this approach is? ● for very sensitive data, synthetic data would be useful to ensure no sensitive information is exposed

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Web scraping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gen-AI web scraped aggregation - e.g. literature review, but also e.g. digs through those papers to find the data source and checks that you can get to the data itself. ● Clarification on distinctions between web 'scraping', 'crawling', 'archiving' ● Major legal and ethical challenges in scraping ● Take down requests / policy. The right to be forgotten. Issue of robots.txt ● Need tools and trainings for how to scrape responsibly, reproducibly etc ● support and resources to encourage best practices - need some key examples that model good behaviour ● dat donated from the community would be very different from the web scraping data, I don' ● Web archiving decouples collection from analysis and preparation - there are places where scraping alone is appropriate, and scraping skills are necessary of course. ● Why web scraping when existing web archiving toolkits offer so much, both at manual and large (automated) scales? ● Web scraped data would be harder to share to other users from legal and ethical perspectives ● Scraping is primarily the act of parsing the content, you see need to do that with web archiving ● Ways to de identify data and check identifiability of scraped data. Ways to scrape according to ethical data collection more generally ● Gen-AI is great for de identification as well - as long as you use it on a platform that is permitted by your ethics and governance. e.g. Local compute for highly sensitive data. Especially good for a first pass on deidentifying data.
(other responses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A shared understand or dictionary of meaning. It will be important to have a common language across users, researchers, and industry/government. ● Visual data created in experiential workshops how to capture the non-written information particularly without ethics? ● The level of technical knowledge needed to source data varies widely across these different possibilities. It is much easier to think of cohesive approaches to sharing and access than to sources.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● There needs to be underlying infrastructure for storing the data securely for sharing with researchers across all these columns -- how will data be identified and stored? Secured? Dan talked about "evidence" last time - where are you keeping the evidence? This applies both for large aggregations but also for researcher's own collections -- how will they share even small amounts of data they collect? ● It would be very useful to model different kinds of users of the proposed NRI. The Biocommons have a very useful model for this that starts with users who just want access to data but lack computational skills to users who have some skills to work with digital data through to those with very high level computational skills ● We'll need to be able to gather participant info and consent; ideally it would be good to build pipelines to enable the donation of GDPR data downloads from popular platforms. Then there can be no question that the user has the right to donate the data

Outcome 2: Sharing analytical methods and increasing technical ability in researchers working with mediated data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Machine Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Boring basics: training and evaluating machine learning models (+2) ● Jupyter Notebook/Lab templates for doing certain tasks ● Will likely overlap with Gen AI as specialised tools for Gen AI to call as an agent in a "AI-planned" workflow ● Simplify ML workloads to point-and-click (improves accessibility and usability) ● Research Software Engineering (RSE) and data science expertise for hire, for training, translation, and advanced research. ● At the front end - an AI agent (research assistant) that can be used to concierge all this ● Integration into research data management (RDM) workflows., from inception - > publishing & archiving. ● ML (and LLMs) are going to show up across all these in contemporary HASS research methods ● remaining critical about AI models and the companies behind them - and the training processes that generated them

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capabilities to facilitate fine-tuning of pre-trained LLMs with domain/context-specific data ● Use soft-cite and dataset on specific journals and publications to generate a feed of tools being used in research ● Totally depends on scenario: CNNs, LMM (these already exist - if you know what to look for they are directly accessible!) ● tooling for local-run models e.g. for sensitive data (+1) ● "tooling for local-run models e.g. for sensitive data" - LLama CCP and LM Studio? ● tools like Gorilla LLM which can enable many methods to be used at the command line from just English which is translated to code by the large language model
Crowdsourcing Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Practical issues for involve access to copyright and regulatory, legal support for collecting social objects especially in context of platform based changes. ● It would be hugely advantageous for the platform to have access to a standing 'representative' population of Australians that could be used for a variety of research projects. What we refer to as a 'panel'. (+1) ● Could this build on Australian Twittersphere that ADO has custodianship over? ● Crowdsource your answers using Gen-AI agents instead of people. ● Bring in diverse communities not usually included in crowdsourcing platforms to work on data directly (+2) ● Knowing how to find and how to use and adapt the tools- ● value the media-creative arts skills more into the future ● There are many advanced crowd sourcing platforms. My own team developed SWARM, repliCATS, ... for US Intelligence/Defence folks) ● "There are many advanced crowd sourcing platforms. My own team developed SWARM, repliCATS, ... for US Intelligence/Defence folks)" - +1 to seeing a AU co-created (acknowledging US DoD funding) platform that is good for crowdsourcing. (I have used SWARM and it's a good example of sovereign infrastructure (more or less). ● user participation and communication - people should be able to see the scientific impact of their participatin (+1) ● OPen source tools and platforms will be important both to build and to collaborate with

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Using a open access style method, have simple analysis software that users could ask questions of the crowdsourced data. ● Trusted community of crowdsourcers, connected to meaningful work (+1)
Text and image analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● natural language interface to automated coding and clustering as a supplement to qualitative data analysis (+1) ● Flowise - low and no-code platform for using Gen-AI in your work. Don't need to learn to code. (+1) ● national platform for image analytics running standard models that can extract data from those images. ● Sentiment/ emotions opinion mining ● have capacity for researchers to explore how models classify and cluster images and text, and the capacity to compare and retrain models with new or context-specific data ● National labelled/annotated images for use by broader community (instead of manual annotation from ImageNet etc) ● Platforms like open interpreter, Jupyter-AI or Code interpreter that can write and execute your analysis after you describe it in common English. (+1) ● "Platforms like open interpreter, Jupyter-AI or Code interpreter that can write and execute your analysis after you describe it in common English." - Text to SQL models ● Multimodal, multidata integration (i.e. ways of integrating multiple sources of data into a common analytic pipeline) ● multimodal analysis - incorporating multiple kinds of media/data (+2) ● Also need to develop some consensus and shared approaches to text and image analysis methods; working with data types, and best practice in NLP etc (+2) ● Reproducible workflows in browser-based tools like WASM, e.g. jupyter notebooks that don't need a server and can run locally. (+3)
Test environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● very useful but also needs careful coordination and constant updating ● Making training accessible and demystifying the platform/s. ● Partnerships between multiple groups working on related tooling -e.g. different research groups working on Instagram could work together on an Instagram test bed and test data, and share the burden of keeping it up to date

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Simulation in the loop: how embedding generative AI simulations can enhance processes such as ethnographic studies, policymaking, etc. ● Multiple audience testing of environment including knowledge base and digital technical trainers ● test environments also need to involve mechanisms or platforms for easy and inclusive participation by people: partners and researchers ● Enable test environments that can be used by non academic/technical people. This will also provide data about what people are interested in understanding or knowing more about. (+3) ● Clearly Cloud based but not sure what to be built/tested/simulated yet ● Simulation on steroids, going well beyond older agent-based modelling approaches - tools that mediate between researcher and back-end modelling (+2)
ADO ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ADO works collaboratively with researchers to develop analytical tools and methods. Some are already available in https://www.digitalobservatory.net.au/resources/ But more could be developed ● Highly modular software and frameworks are a key strength of ADO, these have huge value for adaptation in future research (+3) ● SUDO has access to 8500+ data sets across .gov land in Australia from 150+ Government agencies ● question of sustainability (not limited to ADO) - ensuring sustained maintenance (+3) ● The ADO's approach to training and support for researchers unfamiliar with computational tools and methods is going to be valuable going forward (+1) ● Matching people to these different possibilities will need a LOT of support. ● Well built enabling tools that work together (+1)
Visualisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Visual first methods are important, it's not simply about visualising data at the end of the research process, but also using visual methods to drive insights into data (+5) ● High performance and interactive visualisation for detecting patterns in large-scale datasets. If a researcher wanted to search for data based on criteria, they can do so in the visualisation.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Viz can be baked into to Gen AI- "planned" pipelines as required. Again these pipelines can be give a range of tools/agents which can be called on. ● GenAI can also create a visualisation of your data fro you with minimal user input - enabling you to get the visualisation up-front and then refine it rather than wait ages to get the picture of what's going on in your data. it can suggest appropriate visualisations depending upon the data as well. It can be set up not to need human input initially, and then the researcher can iterate afterwards. ● Visualisations and dashboards would be helpful for participants to engage with data and for researchers ● Big potential (given current reliance on propreitary softwrae like Tableau) - GenAI potentially enables natural language instructions to be given to a visualisation module operating over a dataset from elsewhere in the system ● Big need here for researcher-friendly UX design here - a lot of the methods, data and tools we create here would be used by many more if we kept the end user in mind more and designed the user interface for them, rather than dumping them in a jupyter notebook, an API etc. ● Critical guidelines: when is visualisation not recommended/inappropriate
(other responses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Include use of this or similar data environments to students (high school or higher education. Digital literacy includes improving understanding of what our data is being used for. Key thoughts are about accessibility and understanding as a way to sharing methods and increasing skills. ● Just my 2 cents - not to derail the conversation (I hope!). As much as I love upskilling researchers in terms of coding practice etc. I think a more impactful focus would be on providing platforms in which they can analyse their data and use SoTA statistical , machine learning techniques , and gen-ai assistance without learning how to code, and without learning the specifics of state-of-the-art methods. Effective use of Gen-AI, UX design, and selected platform deployment would enable a fair portion of these. (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● This is a really great list of possible functionalities, but I wonder how different parts of it will be prioritised given doing everything in four years may be challenging (resourcing, time etc.) ● We need a code repository such as Github - hosted nationally within australia (unlike Microsoft Github enterprise managed users for instance) in order to allow us to collaborate nationally, while remaining within legal requirements - e.g. nsw personally identifiable data cannot be shared outside of NSW and australian PII data cannot be shared outside of australia without risking \$m legal penalties.. (+1) ● "We need a code repository such as Github" - Personal data should not be in git -- that's for code -- we do need places to store the actual data ● "We need a code repository such as Github" - +1. Furthermore, a coherent policy around publicly funded source code being in GitHub (a U.S. based organisation subsidiary of Microsoft) is needed. There has long been the misconception that GitHub is open source. It is not. (Git was the open source software project on which GitHub the privately held company started). ● plus 1 for GitHub alternative hosted in Australia and not dependent on Microsoft's whims ● There is a pillar missing here which is promoting/communicating information about the infrastructure to researchers and groups - first stage learning: what is it and what is its purpose, what can you do with it , who can use it and how to access it - all very important. (+5) ● "There is a pillar missing here which is promoting/communicating information about the infrastructure to researchers and groups " - +1 A concerted effort into ""socialising"" research infrastructure is needed, e.g., on-demand explainer videos, panels at existing academic & applied research conferences in Australia & beyond such as ResBaz). ● Also maybe access to a database different approaches. ie collecting a Twitter is now impossible so what do people do now? And how does this vary/change when collecting other types of objects. It seems to me that there are multiple approaches being used in different GLAMS. Scraping vs collecting specific items. Collecting video vs collecting specific objects and understanding their provenance ● This issue applies across all the columns: As we develop analytical tools and methods, these tools as software. As with any software, it is not a

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>one-off development. It would require maintenance to keep it functioning. (+3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In order to achieve any of this, to become more than the sum of our parts, we need to improve coordination, communication, and visibility. Working groups, communities of practice, whatever the preferred structure is - there need to be forums for discussion and coordination, and they need to be visible and open to new people and groups working in that area ● we need to all work together to help fund and justify skills training in the academic environment

Outcome 3: Increasing coherence and collaboration across groups and disciplines working with mediated data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Labelling and annotations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Being mindful of the contextual label/annotation to maintain the meaning/cultural changes overtime. ● Collaborative annotation is an exciting area to look at, but I don't know how that works with some of the types of data (e.g. if registration is restricted to a single user) ● if collecting donated data tools for maintaining metadata about the flow or sequential nature of mediated data within platform's algorithmic feeds. Important that annotation helps to understand not just content of data but how it is organised by algorithmic feeds in context ● TK labels ● Finetuning LLM based annotation + manual verification could speed up the process a lot ● Diverse communities as subject matter experts who can get involved in data labelling is an exciting prospect ● if using mobile capture methods that rely on screenshots or recordings - tools for extracting metadata about platform context and features e.g. buttons, post formats, ad formats, feed placement etc. ● Culturally sensitive statement ● For images, there is a lot of potential for using IIF. It is under-utilised/ implemented in Australia

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● an understanding of the biases and limitations inherent in labelling practices/platforms that also make linking different datasets challenging e.g. wikidata or wikibase for nationality or gender data etc. ● I wonder if you could use GROBID to restructure web data to apply common categories or extract specific fields of information ● Involvement of community and people with lived experience in this ● Most web archives use the same set of standards which capture contextual information around captures (eg Memento protocol, and CDX indexes). These are often baked into the software so provide basic machine readable data from systems that don't have other APIs (eg Australian Web Archive). See: https://glam-workbench.net/web-archives/#types-of-data ● metadata! Who, When, Why? ● Labelling and annotation may involve the creation of private or sensitive information ● Collecting labels from a diverse pool of annotators, e.g., "learning with disagreements" paradigm ● There are many automated data augmentation approaches that are widely used in the deep learning domain ● Use of Standards Terms & ● Ontology, Citation of mediated data ● Techniques to 'unflatten' data that often comes in the form of screenshots or images where these images are originally comprised of texts and image components. And also for videos and audio as well if possible. (+1) ● "Techniques to 'unflatten' data that often comes in the form of screenshots or images" - A tool for labelling and indexing web archives? ● Make it easy and attractive (i.e. rewarding) for researchers to embed their tooling into the platform so it can add value
Harmonisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Depends on scenario, e.g. data with spatial extent can be easily harmonised using knowledge of spatial information ● Harmonisation across data elements for outputs to repurpose and possible new interpretation ● Again, maybe GROBID might help

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discoverability, i.e., helping practitioners knowing what data/resources are available, may help avoiding reinventing the wheel, as well as maintaining compatibility/consistency ● Use of international standards for Identifiers: Orcids, ROR's, RAIDs and instruments etc (+2) ● as with any data modelling problem, this will depend on the analytical method and the particular paradigm required for the project. We don't want to specify one set of columns to rule them all, instead we want to enable contextual transformation of data. ● communicating research back to the public
Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communities can create their own schemas via reseach vocabs australia or for the RO-Crate community build Schema.org-style Schemas for domains eg https://w3id.org/ldac/terms. and metadata profile https://w3id.org/ldac/profile. ● Also involving community and people with lived experience in classification so that standards are not applied from above (+1) ● Have a team that is diverse and transdisciplinary to keep checking the classifications are appropriately following shifts in trends and meaning. ● Not sure what you mean by classification here, e.g. is this a picture of an X? There are few if any systems that adopt an ontology that are robust and used by many researchers ● it would be hard to use ONE classification for everything ● Struggling to wrap my head around classification in most of the use cases we have been talking about - auditing the classification as performed by the platforms could be interesting and important though, as a way of reverse engineering their ways of ordering the data and shaping media experiences for users
Linked Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Linked data requires URIs for stored data and vocabs/ontologies/schemas (which implies infrastructure for storing and identifying data) (+3) ● Linked Data standards are arguably some of the most mature, best documented & widely used by open data publishers. It should be a no-brainer to use Linked Data standards & best practices that have undergone a rigorous peer review & consensus effort by leading digital platform developers (small & large).

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Linking data while useful could increase re-identifiability. Hence, robust precautions and data governance must be in place. ● LDaCA and CDL & co is using RO-Crate (schema.org based data description for both data assets and rich context (eg encyclopaedias) (+5) ● Working with wikidata to develop linked data systems could be effective (+1) ● Large data publishers incl. Gov and GLAM organisations need to be supported to facilitate data publication that facilitates better linking. Eg. PIs, data standards (+1) ● Linking data has been done by many folks for a long time - the question is what kind of linkage and to what end, e.g. death data from AIHW or something else? ● Tools to automate linking and discovery, like 'wizards' that might suggest useful linked data or ways to enrich the data objects contained in specific projects and samples. (+1) ● Ethical/governance guidelines - when is data linkage re-identification, for example? (+2) ● The idea of a recommender system to suggest links can also be useful for data harmonisation and discoverability ● Linked data is different to data linkage, right? (+1) ● good point: need to differentiate data linkage and Linked data
Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication and partnership between groups helps us discover integration opportunities! ● Tools that can work together without a lot of conversions and compatibility issues. (+1) ● "Tools that can work together without a lot of conversions and compatibility issues" - How? Who decides input/output formats? ● standard formats and interfaces (+2) ● Just provide access to remote/federated data that has an API? ● Modular tools allow more variety of integration and workflow assembly (+4) ● data governance and ownership - is the data being transferred between platforms or is the tool being transferred to the data? (+1) ● Data licensing and granular consent is necessary for integration

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The use of PIDs is very important for facilitating integration across data collections (+1)
(other responses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maybe I missed something but I was a bit confused about the idea that this NRI does labelling, annotations, harmonisation, classification, linked data etc. and other facilities are doing identifiers, standards, vocabularies, metadata schemas etc. Aren't the former largely done through the latter? (i.e. the list in yellow is the what, the list below is the how). (+1) ● "Maybe I missed something but I was a bit confused about" - Work is already taking place on the latter - so it's about taking what is out there already and building it into the former (or creating what doesn't already exist) ● Hold space for objective and subjective data. This is important to consider when working with people/social data.

Outcome 4: Develop protocols and guidance for governance and ethics

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need to be mindful that an individual's data may include other's data. Including children and other vulnerable people. ● If I am collecting the data and just holding on to it then am I researching it? Where does the final ethics burden lie? The end user or repository? ● Options for users to request their data be removed are important, and can mitigate some of the difficulties with collecting and using data. (+1) ● "Options for users to request their data be removed are important," - Users would need to know they were in the data first ● This is particularly important (and significantly more challenging) in the context of automated ways of linking/augmenting data from different sources ● Need to develop new resources to explain and support Institutional Ethics committees to understand new data approaches. ● Risk is not always cumulative. Risk can be possibly harmful but exceedingly unlikely. Many things would need to go wrong before the risk actually crystallises. Perhaps a new approach to looking at risk is needed. Potential of risk is not actual risk. (+1)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are different considerations for data archives and research datasets - we need to be clear about what we're discussing. (+2) • modelling and documenting best practices, providing examples • Explanations for what this kind of research involves for various contexts eg for university ethics boards, or for other projects etc • CARE can be guiding principles for data beyond Indigenous data. • Ethics in data interpretation for publication • pro forma ethics statements for ethics applications within universities may help streamline projects for researchers (+1) • Ethics /= Legal Don't conflate the two, ethics relates to humans, legal relates to faceless corporations.
<p>Legal and rights protection</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National platforms for storing sensitive data to required standards so we don't have to reinvent the wheel each time, as well as to enable collaboration across the country. +5 • More clarity around the copyright status of metadata (such as GLAM collection data), as opposed to content. • having legal adviser(s) will be very useful for legal guidance • Need to differentiate legal & rights aspects with ethical aspects (+2) • Supporting a variety of International legal requirements, and local (for example Indigenous) rights and protections will be necessary. This could extend from International to national vs local and tribal expectations and norms Access controls, rather than an assumption of open access will obv be important in this context. • Need to constantly be aware of changes in Terms of Service (ToS) of platforms • We'll need an unusually high level of legal advice (ideally from commercial lawyers NOT university lawyers) (+1) • This project may require an approach to risk that involves a mature sense of our risk appetite when weighing up competing interests - especially around weighting for the public interest. I think here it will often not just involve issues that have a clear legal 'answer', but require judgement around risk and different interests... so we'll probably need the kinds of risk management cultures that you find more often in other sectors.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Data management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In the absence of national and institutional platforms for storage that do NOT come as part of an ARDC Data Commons on LDaCA we have found that we need to DIY this with institutional partners who typically don't have ways to store access-controlled data ● ARDC Nectar research cloud doesn't have a formalised story for hosting/storage beyond the life of a research project (but you can ask for it). A formal story ought to be developed. How does one apply, how is it acted on over years (probably no one has thought about this yet). (+1) ● Platform for storing (sensitive) data == Repository (archive, whatever) ● Lots of people have thought about it, but it's not something ARDC can deliver see the card to the left ● standard, open formats required for preservation and longevity ● KeyPoint = KeyPoint is an eResearch platform that enables data custodians/stewards to manage and share sensitive research data with approved researchers in a scalable, fully governed, and highly secure environment, whilst maintaining full control of their data at all times. ● data management is crucial to preserve ● Data management standards ● sensitive data management and protocols ● the question of platform maintenance and lifespan beyond the grant is key here... where will the data live in three years after the funding has finished? ● Mentoring for next level skills development for specific questions and domains. Training is often at a basic or generic level and hard to get it to apply for specific questions ● sensitive data sharing protocols is essential for a Research Infrastructure on Media(ted) data
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leverage data ethics certification programs such as that are offered by organisations such as the UK Open Data Institute, see https://theodi.org/what-we-do/policy/ and the Professional Certification program, see https://learning.theodi.org/courses/data-ethics-professional-tutor-led ● Note: there are Australian-based researchers who have been certified in the Data Ethics Professional Program. (Speak to Dr David Tarrant @ UK ODI davetaz@theodi.org)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Variety of delivery models - from f2f workshops to written online tutorials ● Focusing training and dev with postgrads and PhDs across disciplines ● Training and skills acquisition over the life cycle of the digital Infrastructure, platforms. Ongoing including knowledge base / technical expertise across upgrades including legacy skills in the use of older /vintage tools ● better resources for ethics committees (+1) ● Trainings and workshops will be crucial to upskill HASS+I researchers ● Work with the Carpentries (+3) ● Summer/winter schools with 'data sprints' where small groups develop projects based using tools (Digital Methods Initiative at UvA has similar model and is great for starting new collaborations) ● Partnerships in training that already happens ● Clear requirements and outcomes ● Inter university materials can be shared across which does not happen yet. ● Possibility of HDR mentorships with professional data wranglers to build skills. LDACA did something like this? (+3) ● "Possibility of HDR mentorships with professional data wranglers to build skills" - They did and it was great! But it's not easy to scale. Needs institutional support and should be built into HDR training as standard ● Outreach/training for members of ethics committees ● Training needed for university research offices, eresearch units, ethics committees as much as researchers (+1) ● Mentored research fellowships (distinct from the placements) - for example LDaCa is running a Graduate Digital Research Fellowship https://www.ldaca.edu.au/news/posts/gdrf/ (+1) ● Provide central infrastructure/templates for organising training/events around specific types of data/issues e.g. a training calendar where people can advertise, templates for organising or running a summer school or data carpentry. This because we need more summer schools/carpentry events around the country for different types of data/issues etc. in addition to more general digital methods, for example.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● An annual digital methods hackathon along the lines of the Amsterdam Digital Methods Summer/Winter school where there are different issues each year and HDRs and researchers gather to experiment and build small projects (which can also be used to develop small software projects for the ARDC) (+1)
Outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Visibility - may look different across different communities. Researchers, research infrastructure providers, government, industry, GLAM community, software and systems community, open source and open data community... ● Need a proactive outreach program to increase uptake of the resources developed ● Community participation in data collaboration and donation is fairly new and needs extensive outreach to support it and build cultures of awareness and willing collaboration ● Important to link this with training - connect with disciplinary associations, summer schools etc. so that it is more integrated with scholarly culture and not seen as 'infrastructure' ● Some resistance can be found in 'not invented here' syndrome, we need ways to talk about the benefits of adopting/collaborating vs. the lone ranger syndrome ● Go to the researchers where they are or they won't know they exist
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sharing (or developing model example) HASS digital data research ethical considerations, participant information sheets etc. (some universities have much better resources than others) (+1) ● Find all the existing tools that are only surviving because of a single person fitting maintenance into their spare time (there are so many labours of love out there that underpin so much other work) and fund them ● Working groups to answer a lot of these questions (vocabulary development etc) ● Reach out to open source, open government, etc groups for collaboration. E.g. Linux Australia for open source software ● Overlapping communities of practice for those developing the tools/infrastructure/methods/trainings etc and those using them

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Huge potential for this project to connect Australian researchers to counterparts internationally - in some ways we are behind, in others we'll be way ahead once this gets going ● There are so many people and groups working in this space - we need to work together rather than just keeping on forming new groups, new platforms in isolation ● Museum of London has done some interesting work in this space as has the library of congress.
Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● thinking about incentives for participation in terms of appropriate recognition for the expertise, knowledge, etc. participants offer by helping researchers understand and access ephemeral forms of digital media. And, thinking also about 'thick' forms of participation where participants go beyond a single instance of donation, but have a more extensive and meaningful engagement with the research process - this needs to be recognised and resourced not just to encourage participation but also to make sure it is valued and that there's equity in terms of who can participate (+1) ● incentives for participation? what is in for participants ● Education around online data use and digital literacy for all. ● Consideration around the possibility that entities may not provide sensitive data to the platform ● protocols for informed consent, dynamic consent, flow-on consent (+1) ● how to ensure representative participation? (+1) ● Science communication - needed between fields as well as between researchers and non-researchers ● Encourage representative participation through paid involvement in data governance, outreach, training etc. ● OUtreach is going to be essential to ensure diverse participation from the public/citizen scientists, given the fragmentation of our national life this will need to be through communities rather than relying on broadcast or word of mouth (+1)
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The UK and EU lead the world (IMHO) on documented practices around legal & rights protection. We should support AU-based applied researchers to collaborate with the working groups, consortia and other communities of practice. Do not recreate the wheel. Leverage what they've done & tailer to AU context.

